

METHODS OF USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PRESCHOOL ENGLISH

Nurniyazov Nursultan Jalgasovich

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

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Annotation: In this article, the opinions, scientific views of scientists and educators on the scientific and theoretical aspects of teaching English science through innovative technologies and interactive methods and the factors of interest in this study have been analyzed and subjective attitude to them have been expressed. Moreover, we can discuss about methods of using modern technologies in teaching preschool English.

Keywords: Independent teaching technologies, methodology of teaching foreign languages, worldview, reflection, speech and communicative competence, expression of attitude, independent thinking, communication, creative and innovative approaches.

In the following years, one of the main tasks is to teach English on the basis of innovative technologies in the teaching process from pre-school teachers to students and students in the educational stages. In our republic, the development of human feelings, such as the multifaceted cooperation with countries of the world on the development of various spheres, the establishment of relations in economic, spiritual and cultural affairs, especially understanding and understanding of each other, appreciation, respect, is closely related to the study of English.

Each teacher in the process of teaching the English language creates the conditions for the formation, development, acquisition of knowledge and its acquisition as a person. On the basis of language learning, it is important for the student to learn science and communicate freely, express opinions and reflect in an independent state, knowing the mathematics of the English language. Therefore, the role of modern methods, interactive methods, support of innovative technologies in the development of their communicative competence, the development of oral and written speech is considered to be significant.

To increase the interest of the reader in learning English to young people, to expand the available opportunities in them, to carry out support work it language will help to learn more quickly. Therefore, it is necessary for the students to carry out the following work on the study of the English language

- carrying out supply work with different electron sources;
- creation of methodological provision for language learning in educational institutions;

- increase the effectiveness of using existing textbooks;
- engaging strong and skilled professionals in the teaching process;
- adequate introduction of new educational technologies into the educational process;
- to control the quality of the system of attention and evaluation on the work of student motivation in teaching.

Control of the quality and effectiveness of English language lessons, obtaining the bulk of the information received from everyday life, is manifested in their growth in the appearance of speech. Evaluation of the use of innovative technologies as a means of Language Teaching and learning in the lesson contributes to the emergence of many positive results, advantages.

Innovation (English" innovation") is the introduction of innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are the pedagogical process, the introduction of innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and readers, and have a significant role in its implementation.

Interactive methods-this is referred to as collective thinking, that is, methods of pedagogical interaction, which is a component of educational content. One of the peculiarities of the interactive techniques is that they are carried out in cooperation with the teacher and students, through the means of joint activities. Such collaborative activities will be the basis for students' obtain knowledge communicative and conversational competences.

The use of innovative technologies is reflected in the work carried out to increase the thinking, imagination, worldview, interest of students. McCartney noted that "the methodology of teaching foreign languages has evolved greatly over the past half century. Conducted at different times in grammatical translation, audio-linguistic structure, global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, ideological, situational, communicative, study/acquisition, recommendation and others." Consequently, as a result of the use of audiovisual tools in the course of the lesson, the ability to remember the semantic meaning of words in memory and to apply lexical units is improved. The main criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in the language portfolio technology are testing. The priority direction of this technology is to direct the educational process from the teacher to the student. The reader, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his cognitive activity.

Conclusion. Advanced modern technologies, innovative approaches and interactive techniques ensure that students-young people are highly educated, have a wide range of high qualifications. It should be said that in order for

students to learn English so that they have knowledge, skills, skills in the grammatical of this language, they are characterized primarily by sufficient knowledge of the grammatical of their native language and complete adherence to it in live speech. One of the lexical units, which is especially active in the speech of students, is the pronoun. At first, knowledge of the native language grammatical about the pronoun, if the skills are formed, will easily understand the same topic in English.

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